

UPDATE, FORMATION AND VISUALIZATION OF BUKHARA NEIGHBORHOOD DATABASES BASED ON USING WITH GIS

Ishkzakova D.D.

Master's degree student in Turin Polytechnic University in Tashkent

[*ishkzakovadinora@gmail.com*](mailto:ishkzakovadinora@gmail.com)

Abstract. A geographic information system (GIS) is a potentially new look in the world around us. In this thesis, information on the use of remote sensing materials and the implementation of urban land monitoring and creation of electronic maps, updating of agricultural maps, remote sensing of the earth and aero-space images is presented.

The succinct chapters are, for the most part, straight for-ward, easy to read, and raise numerous issues for research and discussion. The main components of this system include: It consists of devices such as computers, servers, GPS, mobile devices, etc. Software: Applications used in the GIS field, such as ArcGIS, QGIS, MapInfo, etc. Data: This includes filling the land with GPS and mobile device data, genomes, etc. This system is used in geology, geodesy, urban planning, ecology, and other fields. Once data is analyzed and processed by GIS, we can present it in various ways.

Maps: Maps are powerful tools for visualizing spatial data. They provide context and allow us to communicate information effectively.

Charts: Charts complement maps by representing data in a different format.

Web Maps: Web-based maps are essential for sharing information online.

1.Figure A visualization view of the Bukhara.

The territory is located in Uzbekistan and is called the Bukhara Jewish district. In the process of conducting targeted research work, it became known that the use of existing paper cards as a basis for creating digital and electronic maps of some regions did not give the expected result.

Therefore, in order to solve the issues set before the research work, first of all, it was required to create a cartographic basis. Therefore, in order to reflect the results of the conducted research on maps, we used remote sensing materials to create a cartographic basis.

We have adjusted to update, form, and create a visualization view of the area studied. We need to take measures to achieve high results when updating and monitoring electronic cards based on this GIS software development. This will help obtain important and accurate information in urban architecture, the implementation of historical territories, the creation of their digital passport. Therefore, it is desirable for our society to choose and monitor optimal technical tools, to study the ridge of data collection.

REFERENCES

1. <https://www.bing.com/ck/a>
2. <https://library.fiu.edu/c.php?g=766021&p=5928445>
3. www.GIS.ru
4. Engineering geodesy “Innovative Development Publishing House”. Tashkent – 2021. P. 188/12 (registration number 137-019, 06/04/2016)